

UDC 20

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ARCHITECTURE: PARTNER OR REPLACEMENT

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Annotation: *The article is devoted to the study of the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on such a field of activity as architecture. In the age of rapid development of digital technologies, including AI, many professional fields are at risk of disappearing due to the introduction of high-tech systems. The study aimed to determine the role of AI as an assistant or potential replacement for an architect. In the course of the study of this topic, the methods of literature analysis, comparative method, content analysis, and questionnaire were used. The analysis of the literature allows us to understand the multifunctionality of computer intelligence, since it has long been implemented and is actively used for the automation and convenience of the planning process, as well as the construction of a building. To a certain extent, AI has become an integral tool for architects, but there is still a risk of completely replacing humans in this area. The BIM model acts as an intelligent source of interrelated information about the object and ensures the management of this information throughout the entire life cycle. [1] This way of using AI has developed the field of architecture, raising it to a new level. Despite computer intelligence's ability to process data and generate variants, it is unable to deeply understand human needs, cultural and emotional context, and context that are important in design. [2] The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that its results can be used by architects and educational institutions to optimize design processes, the correct distribution of functions between AI and humans, as well as improve the quality of architectural solutions.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, architecture, construction, planning, replacement, assistant, digital technologies, automation.*

Introduction: In recent years, the rapid development of digital technologies has significantly changed the architectural and construction industry. One of the main factors of these changes is artificial intelligence (AI), which is increasingly involved in the design, analysis and management of construction projects. Modern AI systems are able to study large amounts of data, automate routine procedures, and offer optimal architectural solutions. This makes them a powerful tool in the hands of an architect, but it also provokes discussions about whether AI can completely replace a human specialist in the future. Object of research: the process of architectural design. Subject of research: the role of AI in performing the functions of an architect. The purpose of the study may be to determine the role of artificial intelligence in architecture and to clarify its role mainly as an assistant to the architect or a potential replacement.

The main tasks include:

- to analyze existing works on the use of AI;
- determine which functions AI performs best;
- identify limitations and risks;
- compare the role of the architect and AI in the creative process.

The paper examines modern technologies, including BIM models, generative design and machine learning algorithms, and analyzes their impact on professional activities. Based on the analysis of the literature and the current situation in the construction industry, a hypothesis is put forward: artificial intelligence is acceptable only as an assistant to an architect, but it is not able to completely replace a person in this profession, since it does not have a sense of empathy, and is not

able to create something new. because he learns on existing projects. The results obtained made it possible to better understand how AI is changing the field of architecture, what advantages and risks arise from its implementation, and what areas of development of personnel training are becoming relevant in the context of digitalization of the industry.

Literature review:

In recent years, the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) into architectural design has become one of the most discussed areas in the scientific literature. Many researchers note that AI is really changing the structure of construction activities, automating some of the routine tasks and thereby easing the burden of responsibility on the shoulders of the architect [4]. Another important area of research is the integration of AI with BIM technologies. M. Hamdani and his colleagues believe that the combination of AI and BIM makes it possible to increase the efficiency of modeling, to identify errors at the initial stages of design [5]. This really saves time in the development of project documentation and generally makes the work more manageable and transparent. Considerable attention is paid to generative design. In their study, L. Rivera and co-authors show that generative AI models are able to create dozens of variants of architectural solutions based on specified parameters, accelerating the early stages of design and expanding the variability of shaping [6]. Nevertheless, the authors emphasize that the options provided by AI still require expert verification by the architect, because algorithms cannot take into account the social, cultural, and emotional aspects of the environment.

V. Morsi's research indicates that current AI algorithms are more effective as a decision support tool than as independent designers [7]. Morsi also argues that AI can handle the automation of analytical tasks and the creation of systematized models, but it cannot fully translate the creative thinking and value judgments required in architectural design.

Thus, the analysis of modern literature shows that AI already occupies a stable place in architecture as a tool for optimization, modeling and generation of design solutions. But the opinion of most authors agrees that its role remains auxiliary: AI improves the activities of the architect, but is not able to replace his professional vision and ability to take into account human needs in the designed environment.

Research methods: For a deeper understanding and disclosure of the research topic, several methods are used to provide a thorough analysis of the experience of AI application in the architectural industry.

Questionnaire (survey) is used to collect a primary database on the representation of AI in the field of construction among survey participants of different ages, genders, and areas of study. This method makes it possible to determine public opinion about the effectiveness of AI, as well as to compare objective assessments with theoretical models of application.

Content analysis is used to analyze various sources, i.e. works, articles, publications, reviews of technology companies (Autodesk, Smartvid.io), industry recommendations, presentations. It helps to identify the main areas of AI application.

Literature analysis – study of scientific articles, reports, reviews of technologies (BIM, generative design, AI in architecture). It allows you to understand the current state of the issue and the main trends.

The comparative method is a comparison of the capabilities of AI and a human architect: where AI is more effective (generation of options, calculations, data analysis), where a person is indispensable (creativity, artistic taste, social context).

These methods made it possible to comprehensively assess the impact of artificial intelligence on the profession of architect and identify the key advantages and limitations of its use.

Results and discussion: Through the use of literature analysis methods, content analysis, we were able to collect the necessary factual database for further analysis. Based on the data, we created a survey. In the process of conducting a questionnaire (Charts 1; 2; 3), where the bulk of respondents were women: 64.7%, aged 17-18 years, 52.9%, studying to be architects/designers, 58.8%, we came to certain results.

Charts1; 2; 3- Screening questions for respondent analytics.

Based on the first question in the questionnaire (Chart 4) about the ability of AI to perform tasks without human intervention, the lion's share (70.6%) of respondents noted partiality, i.e., only in routine tasks for automation and time saving.

2. Do you think AI can fully perform the tasks of an architect without human involvement?
17 ответов

Chart 4. - Assessment of AI independence.

In the course of analyzing the importance of AI in architecture, we found that each BIM scenario serves a sequence of work to perform an enlarged function, for example, structural analysis, lighting analysis, planning the use of the construction site [3]. This part of the work plays an important role in the entire design process and thanks to this ability of computer intelligence, a significant amount of time is saved, which cannot but have a positive effect on the entire project as a whole. The responsibilities of the architect include: the development of the concept of the building (the creation of the idea, image, character of the future object; the definition of style, atmosphere, expressive elements), the formation of an architectural and artistic solution (the aesthetics of the form, work with proportions, compliance with the cultural and social context), the design of space for a person (analysis of the needs of future users, behavior scenarios, convenience, comfort, safety). AI adopts the above responsibilities only partially, as it is unable to understand emotions, culture, and social context. The technical responsibilities of the architect include: Creation of drawings and project documentation (layouts, facades, sections, master plans), calculations and analyses (lighting analysis, structural calculations, energy efficiency), work with a BIM model (building modeling, information management throughout the life cycle, coordination of engineering systems), taking into account construction norms and standards (SNiP, fire codes, ergonomics, environmental requirements). Artificial intelligence is already actively adopting these functions. For example: Autodesk

Dreamcatcher, Midjourney V6, Rhino+Grasshopper+AI plugins, Revit AI analytics. Our survey also raises the question (Chart 5) about the most useful AI function in this area, with a higher number of participants indicating structural and safety analysis (76.5%).

4. Which AI functions do you consider most useful for architects? (Select all that apply)
 17 ответов

Chart 5. - Identify useful AI features

In organizational duties, computer intelligence is powerless: coordination of work with engineers, designers, customers; holding meetings, presenting the project, making decisions and quality control. The reasons may be, first of all, that AI does not have an understanding of the real construction processes, no responsibility, and no communication skills with customers. These limitations are mentioned in one of the questions in our survey (Chart 6), where respondents identified the most critical disadvantage of AI: the inability to read cultural and emotional context (64.7%).

5. Which limitations of AI do you consider most critical? (Select all that apply)
 17 ответов

Chart 6. - Identifying the limitations of AI.

In general, we can say that artificial intelligence takes its proper place at the moment: an assistant tool, because it copes well with technical duties, but does not have a sense of empathy and an understanding of culture, and mistakes are also possible. It is possible to predict the impersonality of architecture in the future with the dominance of computer intelligence in this area, because the database will not be updated, and the machine system is devoid of creativity. The prevailing number (76.5%) of survey participants share the same opinion (Chart 7.)

7. What do you think is the optimal way to use AI in architecture?
 17 ответов

Chart 7. - Determining the role that AI occupies.

Conclusion:

As a result of the study, it was revealed that artificial intelligence occupies an important place in modern architectural practice, but its role remains mainly auxiliary. The analysis of the literature, the results of the survey and the considered examples of AI application confirm that the new algorithms effectively perform the functions of automating routine processes - data analysis, creation of BIM models, generation of design options and identification of errors. These features help make the design process more accurate, as well as reduce time spent and streamline the architect's workflow. However, despite the rapid growth of technological development, AI is still not able to fully replace the architect. The industry requires creative thinking, an understanding of cultural context, human emotional needs, and social responsibility – aspects that are not inherent in algorithms. Logic and calculation are not the only criteria in design, it also requires the ability to artistically comprehend space, which is exclusively human competence.

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